

Synthesis of Coumarin Derivatives as Possible Antifungal and Antibacterial Agents

A. K. SENGUPTA*, SRIRUPA SEN and VERSHA SRIVASTAVA

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University, Lucknow-226 007

Thirty new coumarin derivatives have been synthesised. In the first scheme 15 new heterocyclic derivatives of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin have been synthesised. These were screened for antifungal and antibacterial activities. In the second scheme Mannich bases and benzylidene derivatives of coumarin substituted rhodanines have been synthesised. The structure of the compounds were confirmed by spectral and microanalytical data.

It has been reported that heterocyclic compounds particularly those having six- or five-membered ring have occupied the first place among various classes of organic compounds for their diverse biological activities¹.

Coumarin ring has easy acceptability in the biological system as compared to isomeric, isosteric chromone nucleus². Coumarin are the best known aromatic lactones³. Several coumarin derivatives possess pesticidal, fungicidal, anticoagulant and bactericidal activities⁴. Ahluwalia⁵ showed that compounds in which coumarin ring is directly attached to a heterocyclic ring exhibit pesticidal activity. 7-O-Ether of 7-hydroxycoumarin and substituted hydrazides possess various biological activities⁶. Another important group of fungicides and bactericides are constituted of dithiocarbamates. Rhodanines formed by the cyclisation of dithiocarbamate have also been found to be inherently toxic to bacteria and fungi thus evoke considerable attention⁷.

In view of the pesticidal property of hydrazides and various nitrogen heterocyclic compounds, it was of interest to synthesise various coumarin derivatives having the above moieties incorporated in it. In Scheme 1, coumarin was coupled with important heterocyclic thiazolidones, pyrazole, pyrazolone, oxadiazole, triazole to synthesise new moiety by the cyclocondensation of biologically active hydrazides (2).

The reaction of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin with chloroethyl acetate was carried out in presence of anhydrous K_2CO_3 and dry acetone giving rise to ethyl (4-methyl-7-coumarinyloxy)acetate (1) in quantitative yield. Treatment of 1 with hydrazine hydrate in presence of ethanol as solvent gave 4-methyl-7-coumarinyloxyacetic acid hydrazide (2) in good yield.

The cyclocondensation of 2 with ethyl acetoacetate and acetylacetone gave pyrazolone (12) and pyrazole (11) respectively. While treatment of 2 with aryl isothiocyanate gave (4-methyl-7-coumarinyloxy)acetic acid-N-(phenyl substituted)-hydra-

zine carbothiamide (3a-e). Cyclocondensation of 3 with 4 N NaOH afforded 4-phenyltriazole-3-thiol (4a-c) and cyclisation of 3 with I_2/KI in NaOH gave oxadiazole (5a-c). The reaction between different substituted aldehydes and hydrazide (2) in presence of traces of glacial acetic acid yielded N-(substituted-benzylidene) (4-methyl-7-coumarinyloxy)acetic acid hydrazone (7d-g) which on further cyclocondensation with mercaptoacetic acid afforded substituted-thiazolidone (8d-g); on the other hand the interaction of 2 with CS_2 in presence of alcoholic KOH afforded oxadiazole-5-thiol (9) in moderate yield which on treatment with hydrazine hydrate gave aminotriazole (10).

The introduction of coumarin moiety in rhodanine might result in the development of fungicides of choice as the efficacy of substituted-coumarin as bactericidal and fungicidal⁸ agents is well-established. Earlier studies on Mannich bases of coumarin⁹ revealed that introduction of substituted-amino group in a coumarin ring system enhances its biological activities. Gupta and Sengupta¹⁰ reported several benzylidene derivatives of rhodanines as potent fungicides.

These findings have prompted us to synthesise some benzylidene and Mannich bases of rhodanine substituted with coumarin. In Scheme 2, coumarin substituted with rhodanine at 3-position were prepared by the procedure similar to that adopted by Brown *et al.*¹¹. 3-Aminocoumarin was treated with CS_2 and ammonia followed by sodium chloroacetate in alkaline medium to give carbomethyl dithiocarbamate (1), which on cyclisation with acetic anhydride gave the corresponding rhodanine (2). Benzylidene derivatives of 2 were obtained by Knoevenagel reaction with different aldehydes and Mannich bases were obtained with primary and secondary amines in presence of formaldehyde.

The formation of rhodanine was supported by elemental analysis ir, nmr and mass spectral data. The ir spectra showed bands around 1660, 1350 and 1200 cm^{-1} characteristic of 3-5-disubstituted-rhodanine¹². The band for coumarin appeared

in the vicinity of 1720 cm^{-1} . While in case of Mannich bases, the bands at $1175-1390$ (CN stretch¹³) confirmed the structure of compounds.

The compounds were highly crystalline with sharp melting points and showed moderate pesticidal activity.

Biological activity : With the presumption that 4-methyl-7-coumarinyloxy moiety by virtue of incorporating toxophoric nitrogen heterocyclic rings (oxadiazole, thiazolidone, pyrazole, triazole and pyrazolones) would be potent antibacterial and antifungal agents, 15 such compounds were tested. The various coumarin substituted with heterocyclic moiety (Table 1) were found to be devoid of good antibacterial activity. Only two compounds **5b** and **5c** were found to be active against *Staphylococcus aureus*. It was found that substitution of oxadiazole moiety with 4-methyl-7-coumarinyloxy moiety showed remarkable activity against bacteria.

All compounds were screened for their inhibitory effects against *Aspergillus niger*, *Chaetomium*

globosum, *Fusarium celmonum*, *Pullularia pullulans*, *Cladospennium* spp. and *Trichoderma viridi* using some of the test compounds in 5% DMF in acetone by agar plate diffusion technique¹⁴.

In screening of 15 compounds it was found that fungi could not resist the activity of compounds **5b**, **5c**, **9** and **10** completely ; thus these compounds possess good antifungal activity against all six fungi. In view of the structure-activity relationship the appreciable inhibition was observed by the oxadiazole ring substituted at 7-position of 4-methyl-7-coumarinyloxy moiety. Exception to the rule was the one of triazole ring substituted with coumarin (**10**) also found active against fungi. The other compounds did not show any remarkable inhibitory action.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The compounds were checked by tlc. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrometer, nmr spectra

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (Scheme 1)

Compd. no.	R	Yield %	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Solubility	Analysis : Found/(Calcd.)		
						O	H	N
3a	OH ₂	75	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄ S	205	DMF	60.10 (60.45)	4.25 (4.78)	10.32 (10.57)
3b	Br	70	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄ SBr	210	DMF	49.08 (49.80)	4.25 (4.11)	9.11 (9.09)
3c	H	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄ S	170	DMF	59.27 (59.58)	4.60 (4.48)	10.54 (10.96)
7d	Cl	80	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	268	DMF	61.85 (61.62)	4.12 (4.05)	7.82 (7.56)
7e	NO ₂	82	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄	292	DMF	59.51 (59.84)	3.66 (3.98)	11.15 (11.02)
7f	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OH	80	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄	210	MeOH	62.55 (62.82)	4.17 (4.71)	7.71 (7.82)
7g	(OH ₂) ₂ N	75	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄	220	MeOH + CHCl ₃	66.15 (66.49)	5.68 (5.54)	11.25 (11.08)
4a	OH ₂	70	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄ S	205	MeOH	61.28 (61.76)	4.65 (4.41)	10.45 (10.29)
4b	Br	60	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄ SBr	115	MeOH	50.24 (50.78)	3.53 (3.15)	8.42 (8.89)
4c	H	70	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄ S	262	CHCl ₃	60.28 (60.91)	4.15 (4.06)	10.28 (10.65)
5a	OH ₂	50	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄	100	CHCl ₃	66.35 (66.11)	4.63 (4.40)	11.86 (11.57)
5b	Br	55	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ Br	68	MeOH	53.54 (53.27)	3.51 (3.27)	9.42 (9.81)
5c	H	60	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄	98	MeOH	65.61 (65.32)	4.51 (4.29)	12.23 (12.03)
6a	OH ₂	60	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₄ S	128	CHCl ₃	60.25 (60.41)	4.61 (4.84)	9.84 (9.61)
8d	Cl	65	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ SCl	76	DMF	56.28 (56.75)	3.41 (3.82)	6.51 (6.90)
8e	NO ₂	70	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₇ S	118	DMF	55.51 (55.38)	3.52 (3.73)	9.68 (9.23)
8f	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OH	50	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₇ S	115	DMF	57.95 (57.89)	4.52 (4.38)	9.45 (9.21)
8g	N(CH ₃) ₂	70	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₄ S	above 300	MeOH	60.55 (60.92)	5.32 (5.07)	9.51 (9.27)
9	—	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄ S	232	MeOH	53.24 (53.79)	3.94 (3.48)	9.28 (9.65)
10	—	50	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₄ S	185	MeOH	51.54 (51.31)	3.61 (3.94)	18.85 (18.42)
11	—	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄	175	CHCl ₃	65.51 (65.38)	5.31 (5.12)	8.52 (8.97)
12	—	70	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄	135	Dioxane	61.32 (61.14)	4.81 (4.45)	8.85 (8.91)

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (Scheme 2)

Compd. no.	R	Yield %	M.p. °C	Solubility	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
						O	H	N
4a		60	258	CHCl ₃ + DMF	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂ O ₄	54.10 (54.25)	4.48 (4.28)	7.12 (7.44)
4b		55	200	CHCl ₃ + DMF	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	61.42 (61.11)	4.21 (4.44)	11.24 (11.55)
4c		62	250	CHCl ₃ + DMF	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂ O ₄	54.92 (54.98)	2.41 (2.89)	6.84 (6.74)
4d		65	185	Acetone	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂ O ₄	59.80 (59.84)	3.11 (3.41)	7.01 (7.94)
4e		50	260	DMF	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂ O ₄	60.28 (60.75)	3.58 (3.79)	7.85 (7.08)
4f		40	204	DMF	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ S ₂ O ₄	59.21 (59.50)	4.48 (4.70)	7.29 (7.75)
4g		45	215	DMF	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	62.31 (62.06)	4.28 (4.95)	9.59 (9.05)
5h		50	92	MeOH	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ NO ₂ S ₂ Cl	57.00 (57.14)	2.85 (2.50)	3.21 (3.50)
5i		60	168	MeOH	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂ O ₄	55.92 (55.56)	2.14 (2.18)	6.58 (6.82)
5j		70	180	MeOH	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ NS ₂ O ₄	59.81 (59.84)	2.52 (2.88)	3.43 (3.67)
5k		68	115	MeOH	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ S ₂ O ₄	60.52 (61.76)	3.41 (3.92)	3.69 (3.48)
5l		72	190	MeOH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₂ S ₂	59.48 (59.29)	3.32 (3.52)	3.54 (3.29)
5m		68	158	MeOH	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ NO ₂ S ₂	58.04 (58.89)	3.41 (3.16)	3.82 (3.40)
5n		62	168	MeOH	C ₁₇ H ₉ NO ₂ S ₂	57.12 (57.46)	2.81 (2.53)	3.52 (3.94)
5o		66	157	MeOH	C ₁₇ H ₉ NO ₂ S ₂	54.55 (54.98)	2.88 (2.42)	3.12 (3.77)

TABLE 3—SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (Scheme 1)

Compd. no.	ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹	δ	m/e
4a	1 730 (lactonic C=O), 1 260 (C-O-C), 2 420 (SH), 2 950 (OH of CH ₂), 1 590 (C=N) presence of 1 160 (C=S) and 3 300 (NH) bands showed the predominance of thiol form, confirm the tautomeric mixture	2 84 (6H, s, 2 × CH ₂), 4 92 (2H, s, OOH ₂), 6.16 (H, s, SH), 6.7-6.9 (8H, m, ArH of coumarin), 7.15-7.8 (4H, s, ArH of triazole), 7.4-7.5 (H, d, J 9.5 Hz, OH of coumarin)	407 (M ⁺), 108, 146, 98
5a	1 730 (lactonic C=O), 1 260 (C-O-C), 1 570 (C=N), 2 965 (OH of CH ₂), 3 280-3 340 (NH)	2.2 (3H, s, CH ₃), 8.8-8.9 (1H, bs, NH), 3.4 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 7.1-7.45 (7H, m, ArH), 7.5-7.6 (1H, d, J, 9.5 Hz, OH of coumarin)	368, 362 (M ⁺), 108

(Table 3 contd.)

8e	1 740 (lactonic C=O), 2 995 (OH of OH ₂), 3 450 (NH), 1 680 (C=O of thiazolidone), 1 000 (C-S-O), 2 985 (OH ₂), 1 260 (C-O-O)	2.3 (3H, s, OH ₂), 5.0 (2H, s, CH ₂ of thiazolidone), 5.2 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 8.9-9.1 (1H, bs, NH), 7.7-7.95 (7H, m, ArH), 7.5-7.6 (H, d, J 9.5 Hz, OH of coumarin)	454 (M ⁺), 106, 368, 246, 184, 148, 92
9	1 710 (lactonic C=O), 2 900 (OH of OH ₂), 1 220 (C-O-O), 1 510 (C=N), 2 410 (SH), 1 160 (C=S), 3 100 (NH), bands showed its tautomeric thiol form	2.4 (3H, s, OH ₂), 5.2 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 6.1 (H, s, SH), 6.85-7 (3H, m, ArH), 7.5-7.62 (1H, d, J 9.5 Hz, OH of coumarin)	290, 289 (M ⁺), 106, 167, 120, 92, 91
10	1 740 (lactonic C=O), 1 240 (C-O-O), 3 350 (NH ₂), 2 560 (SH), 1 600 (C=N), 1 175 (C=S)	9.8 (1H, s, NH ₂), 6.84 (H, s, SH), 2.4 (3H, s, OH ₂), 5.1 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 7.5-7.59 (H, d, J 9.5 Hz, OH of coumarin), 6.9-7 (3H, m, ArH)	303 (M ⁺), 282, 165, 104, 118, 94, 89
11	1 740 (lactonic C=O), 1 200 (C-O-O), 2 985 (OH of OH ₂), 2 900 (OH of OH ₂), 3 008 (OH), 1 540 (C=N)	2.85 (3H, s, OH ₂), 2.48 (3H, s, OH ₂), 2.25 (3H, s, OH ₂), 5.4 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 5.9-6.1 (H, d, J 10 Hz, OH), 6.7-6.9 (3H, m, ArH), 7.44 (9H, d, J 9.5 Hz, OH of coumarin)	312 (M ⁺), 818 (M+1), 269, 234, 158, 146, 108, 96
12	1 720 (lactonic C=O), 2 980 (OH of OH ₂), 1 220 (C-O-O), 1 700-1 680 (C=O), 2 900 (OH of OH ₂), 1 560 (C=N), 3 100 (hydrogen in enol form)	2.4 (3H, s, OH ₂), 2.25 (3H, s, OH ₂), 6.1 (H, s, OH), 7.1-7.5 (3H, m, ArH), 5.4 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 7.8-8.0 (1H, d, OH of coumarin)	314, 313 (M ⁺), 262, 234, 164, 146, 109, 97

TABLE 4—SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (Scheme 2)

Compd. no.	ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹	δ	m/s
3	1 725 (lactonic C=O), 1 620 (OH=O), 3 350 (OH), 1 660 (C=O rhodanine), 1 350 (C-N), 1 200 (C=S)	7.82 (4H, s, ArH), 6.4 (1H, s, OH), 2.2 (2H, s, OH ₂)	277, 276 (M ⁺), 202, 162, 133
4a	1 740 (lactonic C=O), 1 630 (OH=O), 3 250 (OH), 1 640 (C=O rhodanine), 1 300 (C-N), 1 220 (C=S), 1 160 (C-O-O)	—	375, 374 (M ⁺), 334, 277, 162, 184, 119, 91
5h	1 740 (lactonic C=O), 1 700 (OH of thio), 3 400 (OH), 1 320 (C-N), 1 200 (C=S), 1 160 (OCH ₂), 1 640 (C=O), 1 620 (OH=O)	7.2-7.6 (7H, m, ArH), 8.5 (1H, s, OH), 2.1 (3H, s, OCH ₂)	398/397 (M ⁺), 364/368, 162, 184, 119, 91

(CDCl₃+DMSO-d₆) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on a Jeol-JMS D-300 instrument.

7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin¹⁶, ethyl (4-methyl-7-coumarinyloxy)acetate (1)¹⁶ and (4-methyl-7-coumarinyloxy)acetic acid hydrazide (2)¹⁷ were prepared by the reported methods.

N-(Substituted-benzylidene)(4-methyl-7-coumarinyloxy)acetic acid hydrazide (7d-g): A solution of the hydrazide (2; 0.01 mol) in ethanol was warmed, cooled and to it appropriate aldehyde (0.01 mol) and a few drops of glacial acetic acid were added. The mixture was refluxed for 6 h and the separated solid was washed with cold ethanol and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid to give a white amorphous solid (7d; 80%), m.p. 263°.

7-[(2-Substituted-phenyl-4-oxo-3-thiazolidinyl)-carbomoyl]methoxy-4-methylcoumarin (8d-g): A mixture of 3 (0.01 mol) and thioglycolic acid (0.01

mol) in dioxane (15 ml) was refluxed using Dean-Stark water separator till 1.8 cm³ (0.01 mol) of water was separated. The solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure and reaction mixture cooled and extracted with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution. The bicarbonate extract was acidified with dilute HCl and the resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from dimethyl formamide to give a yellow amorphous solid (8d; 65%) m.p. 76°.

[(4-Methyl-2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran)-7-yl]oxy]acetic acid 2-[(4-substituted-phenyl)amino]thioxomethyl]hydrazide (3a-c): To a solution of the hydrazide (2; 0.01 mol) in ethanol were added substituted phenyl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) and a drop of glacial acetic acid and the mixture was refluxed for 6 h. It was then cooled, filtered and removal of solvent yielded fine crystals which were recrystallised from dioxane (3a; 75%), m.p. 205°.

Scheme 1

2-Arylamino-5-[(4-methyl-2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-7-yl)oxy]-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (5a-c): To the carbothiamide (3; 0.01 mol) dissolved in minimum quantity of ethanol was added 6N NaOH (15 ml). A 5% solution of iodine in KI was then added dropwise and the reaction mixture kept at 10°. The addition of iodine was continued till the colour of iodine persisted and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 h at 70–80°. On cooling, the separated solid was washed thoroughly with water and recrystallised from methanol–chloroform to give a brown solid (5a; 50%), m.p. 100°.

5-[(4-Methyl-2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran)-7-yl]-2,4-dihydro-4-phenyl-3H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiones (4a-c): A mixture of the carbothiamide (3; 0.01 mol) in 4N NaOH was refluxed for 2 h at 150–60°. It was then cooled and neutralised with dilute HCl and the resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from chloroform to give a white solid (4a; 70%), m.p. 205°.

4-Methyl-[(3-methyl-5-oxo-3-pyrazolin-1-yl)carbonyl]methoxyl coumarin (12): A solution of the hydrazide (2; 0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was treated with freshly distilled ethyl acetoacetate (0.15 mol) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 12 h. The solvent removed under reduced pressure and the resulting solid was washed with ethanol and recrystallised from dioxane to give crystalline solid (12; 70%), m.p. 135°.

7-[(3,5-Dimethylpyrazol-1-yl)carbonyl]methoxy]-4-methylcoumarin (11): A solution of the hydrazide (2; 0.01 mol) dissolved in dry absolute ethanol (15 ml) was added (0.01 mol) to acetylacetone and the mixture refluxed for 12 h. The solvent was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the resulting solid was washed with cold ethanol and recrystallised from chloroform to give a white crystalline solid (11; 70%), m.p. 175°.

2-[(4-Methyl-2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-7-yl)oxy]methyl]-1,3,4-oxadiazole-5-thiol (9): To a mixture of the hydrazide (2; 0.01 mol) and KOH (0.15 mol) in dry ethanol (20 ml) was added CS₂ (0.01 mol) dropwise and refluxed for 6 h under dry environment. The excess of solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure and the content poured over crushed ice. The resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from methanol to give a yellow solid (9; 65%), m.p. 232°.

4-Amino[(4-methyl-2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-7-yl)oxy]methyl]-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (10): To a solution of 9 (0.01 mol) dissolved in ethanol (15 ml) was added hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) and the reaction mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 8 h. On cooling the solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure and the resulting solid was washed with cold ethanol and recrystallised from ethanol to give a yellow solid (10; 50%), m.p. 185°.

3-Aminocoumarin: It was prepared by literature method¹⁸.

Ammonium N-(coumarin-3-yl) dithiocarbamates (1): Carbon disulphide (0.11 mol) was added dropwise to a stirred mixture of 3-aminocoumarin (0.10 mol) and ammonia solution (15 ml; sp. gr. 0.88) in ethanol and ether at 0–5°. The mixture was stirred for 2–4 h at room temperature and left overnight. The resulting solid dithiocarbamate was washed with ether and dried to yield 1 (60%), m.p. 115°.

Carboxymethyl N-(coumarin-3-yl) dithiocarbamates (2): A solution of sodium chloroacetate (0.10 mol) in water (25 ml) was adjusted to pH 7.1–7.5 with dilute Na₂CO₃ solution. Aqueous suspension of ammonium dithiocarbamate (1) was then added dropwise to it with stirring at 30–5° and stirring continued for 5–6 h at room temperature. It was then cooled, neutralised with acetic acid and pH adjusted to about 4 with 6N HCl. The resulting solid was washed with cold water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol to yield 2 (55%), m.p. 140°.

Scheme 2

3-Coumarin-3-yl rhodanines (3): Compound 2 (0.05 mol) in acetic anhydride (50 ml) was heated on a steam-bath at 80–90° for 20–25 min till the colour of the solution changed from yellow to brown. It was then cooled and a mixture of water and acetic acid (50 ml; 1:1) added. On cooling rhodanine separated as brown shining needles (3; 56%), m.p. 198°.

5-((Substituted)methylene)-3-(2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-3-yl)-2-thioxo-4-thiazolidinone (5h-o): To rhodanine (3; 0.01 mol) taken in absolute ethanol, were added appropriate aldehyde (0.01 mol) and a drop of piperidine and the mixture was refluxed for 10–12 h on a water-bath. Ethanol was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol to give a brown solid (5h; 50%), m.p. 92°.

5-(Substituted)methyl-3-(2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-3-yl)-2-thioxo-4-thiadiazolidinone (4a-g): To rhodanine (3; 0.01 mol) dissolved in methanol was added formaldehyde (0.15 mol) dropwise and refluxed on a water-bath. Then primary and secondary amine (0.01 mol) and a few drops of HCl were added to it and refluxed for 10–15 h. The resulting solid was washed with methanol and recrystallised from chloroform to give white shining crystals (4a; 60%), m.p. 258°.

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